

THE NETTING ANALYSIS AS A LIMIT CASE OF THE LAMINATED STRUCTURE THEORY

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Keywords: netting analysis, classical laminated plate theory, sensitivity analysis

1 Introduction

The netting analysis is immediately discarded or even not presented in the classical references on the mechanics of composite materials, such as the books by Tsai and Hahn [1], by Jones [2] and numerous others. It is almost never referred in the literature on composites. However, even before the advent of the so-called advanced composites, pressure vessels designed according to the netting theory have been developed, manufactured and used, and still are.

The purpose of this paper is to show that the netting theory is in fact a limit case of the classical laminated structure theory, and so can explain and predict the major trends of the behaviour of composite structures.

2 Outline and discussion of the netting theory

The netting analysis applies to membrane loading of thin structures reinforced with fibres in several directions. It assumes that the loads are entirely carried by these fibres, with a repartition between the directions determined by the free-body diagram of the external loads. This is considered to apply to both the stiffness and the strength.

Comments found in the literature for the usefulness and the accuracy of the netting analysis are contradictory: Peters and Humphrey [3] admitted it is "an excellent basis for quick sizing", Humphreys and Rosen [4] considered it "can be used as an approximation", while Jones [2] rejected it as "grossly" inaccurate. None of these authors quotes the sources of the works demonstrating their comments. Roylance [5] presented an analysis of burst test data of cylindrical bottles, in which agreement is poor between netting analysis and gage measurements, however he as-

cribed the gap "primarily to gaging errors."

The assumptions above do not relate to the classical plate theory assumptions. Further the static method of the free-body diagram to distribute the loads applies for only two directions and is indeterminate when there are more directions of fibers.

3 Limit case of the laminated plate theory

The main point in the present approach is that the classical laminated plate theory (CLPT [1], [2]) can be applied together with the stress-strain assumption of the netting analysis. It can be shown that this reproduces the netting analysis results, solves some of its drawbacks, and provides a tool for sensitivity analysis. Due to the simplification of the stress-strain relationship, close-form solutions can be obtained for many configurations. Notations used in the following formulas are explained in the Appendix A-1.

3.1 Some facts from the classical laminated plate theory

Limiting here to the membrane behaviour, the well-known generalized stress-strain relationship of a laminated plate writes:

$$\mathbf{N} = \mathbf{A} \bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}$$

in which \mathbf{N} is the membrane force tensor, \mathbf{A} is the membrane stiffness tensor and $\bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}$ is the mean strain tensor.

By dividing by the total thickness h , this can be transformed into:

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \bar{\mathbf{Q}} \bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}$$

in which $\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \mathbf{N}/h$ is the mean stress tensor and $\bar{\mathbf{Q}} = \mathbf{A}/h$ is the mean membrane stiffness tensor.

Inverting the mean membrane stiffness $\bar{\mathbf{Q}}$ gives the mean membrane compliance $\bar{\mathbf{S}}$, so that:

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = \bar{\mathbf{S}} \bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$$

According to the hypothesis of CLPT, the strains in any ply are equal to the mean strains $\bar{\epsilon}$, while the stresses vary from ply to ply and differ from the mean stresses $\bar{\sigma}$. However, the local stresses in any ply can be expressed from the mean stresses $\bar{\sigma}$, as derived below.

At this stage, it is important to view clearly the effects of the axes in which computation is done, so we use the notations explained in the Appendix A-1. In the local axes, the stresses in the k ply are expressed from the mean strains as:

$$[[\sigma]]_k^k = [[Q]]_k^k [[\bar{\epsilon}]]_k$$

while, when using the values of the strains in the laminate axes, they express as:

$$[[\sigma]]_k^k = [[Q]]_k^k [[R]]_{k \leftarrow 0} [[\bar{\epsilon}]]_0$$

in which $[[R]]_{k \leftarrow 0}$ is the rotation matrix from overall to local axes.

The above formula expressing the mean strains from the mean compliance and the mean stresses writes in the laminate axes:

$$[[\bar{\epsilon}]]_0 = [[\bar{S}]]_0 [[\bar{\sigma}]]_0$$

So the local stresses in the k ply can be expressed from the mean applied stresses $\bar{\sigma}$, as:

$$[[\sigma]]_k^k = [[Q]]_k^k [[R]]_{k \leftarrow 0} [[\bar{S}]]_0 [[\bar{\sigma}]]_0$$

3.2 The netting theory versus the classical laminated plate theory

The netting theory assumption for the stress-strain behaviour, as described in [4], results in the following stiffness matrix for a unidirectional ply, measured in the axes defined by the fibre direction:

$$[[Q]]_0^0 = E \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

where E is the Young's modulus.

This stiffness matrix is singular, so the compliance matrix is not defined for the ply. However this stiffness can be used in the CLPT, which combines stiffnesses of the plies, conveniently rotated, to obtain the total membrane stiffness.

Which such ply stiffness, the total membrane stiffness is singular when there are only two directions

of fibres or plies. It is regular for three or more distinct directions, whatever the numbers of plies in each direction are.

When the membrane stiffness \bar{Q} is regular, it can be inverted to give the mean membrane compliance \bar{S} .

When the total membrane stiffness is singular, the situation is more complex. Mathematically, a compliance can still be defined, using the generalized inverse concept (see [6], [7] and Appendix A-2). Physically, it means that there exists some combination(s) of loads which cannot be supported by the structure. This will be illustrated hereafter.

For regular as well as singular stiffness and compliance matrices, the local stresses in the plies are still expressed by the general formula above, however they get a special form. When developing the formula, it is found that, whatever the load and the Young's modulus are, this local stress is uniaxial in the direction of the ply, i.e.:

$$[[\sigma]]_k^k = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{kk} \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}_k$$

which is in conformity with the hypothesis of the netting analysis.

It follows that this stress in the direction of the fibers in the ply k at angle θ_k is expressed in matrix form as:

$$\sigma_{kk} = [1 \ 0 \ 0] [[Q]]_k^k [[R]]_{k \leftarrow 0} [[\bar{S}]]_0 [[\bar{\sigma}]]_0$$

Performing matrix products, with $a = \cos \theta_k$ and $b = \sin \theta_k$, gives:

$$\sigma_{kk} = E [a^2 \ b^2 \ \sqrt{2}ab] [[\bar{S}]]_0 [[\bar{\sigma}]]_0$$

4 Typical structures

Simple examples hereafter will illustrate the fact that the netting theory is obtained as a limit case of the classical laminated plate theory. They are selected among classical stacking sequences, such as cross-ply, angle-ply, $[0_i / +45_j / -45_k / +90_l]$.

4.1 Cross-ply reinforcement

Let the first axis be in the direction of the fibres of the ply with the highest proportion p (so that $1/2 \leq p \leq 1$).

The mean stiffness is obtained from the CLPT with stacking $[0_p/90_{1-p}]$. In the axes (1, 2) referred to with subscript 0, it is:

$$[[\bar{\mathbf{Q}}]_0 = E \begin{bmatrix} p & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1-p & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Mathematically, this stiffness is singular with rank equal 2. The kernel is proportional to:

$$[[\mathbf{K}]_0 = \tau \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \sqrt{2} \end{bmatrix}$$

which means that the structure cannot sustain loads of such type, i.e. shearing load $\bar{\sigma}_{12} = \tau$. This is obvious from a physical point of view.

The mean compliance is obtained as a generalized inverse of the mean stiffness:

$$[[\bar{\mathbf{S}}]_0 = \frac{1}{E} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{p} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{1-p} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

It is also singular with rank equal 2 and its meaning is restricted to strains and stresses with zero shear, i.e. $\bar{\varepsilon}_{12} = 0$ and $\bar{\sigma}_{12} = 0$

While unable to support shear loading, the cross-ply structure can accommodate any tensile load in the directions of the fibres, $\bar{\sigma}_{11}$ and $\bar{\sigma}_{22}$, that is, any biaxial load of the following form (orthogonal to the kernel):

$$[[\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}]_0 = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\sigma}_{11} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{22} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Using the general formula above giving the local stress in a sheet of fibres from the overall loading, we have:

$$\sigma_{00}^0 = \frac{\bar{\sigma}_{11}}{p} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_{9090}^0 = \frac{\bar{\sigma}_{22}}{1-p}$$

which means that each lamina supports all of the load in its direction, with a magnifying factor equal to the inverse of its proportion. This is in agreement with the hypotheses of the netting analysis.

4.2 Angle-ply reinforcement

Fibres are placed in two directions with the same proportion. The first axis is selected so that the two direction angles are $\pm\varphi$, with $0 < \varphi < \pi/4$ (the limit cases are excluded, as $\varphi = 0$ is in fact a unidirectional reinforcement, while $\varphi = \pi/4$ is a balanced cross-ply reinforcement studied above).

The mean stiffness, obtained from the CLPT with stacking $[\pm\varphi]$, is in the overall axes:

$$[[\bar{\mathbf{Q}}]_0 = E \begin{bmatrix} c^4 & s^2c^2 & 0 \\ s^2c^2 & s^4 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2s^2c^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

in which $c = \cos \varphi$ and $s = \sin \varphi$.

Mathematically, this stiffness is singular with rank equal 2 and a kernel proportional to:

$$[[\mathbf{K}]_0 = t \begin{bmatrix} +s^2 \\ -c^2 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

so the structure cannot support a load of this type.

The generalized inverse of the mean stiffness is the mean compliance, singular too with rank 2 and the same kernel:

$$[[\bar{\mathbf{S}}]_0 = \frac{1}{E} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{c^4}{(c^4+s^4)^2} & \frac{s^2c^2}{(c^4+s^4)^2} & 0 \\ \frac{s^2c^2}{(c^4+s^4)^2} & \frac{s^4}{(c^4+s^4)^2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2s^2c^2} \end{bmatrix}$$

The structure supports any load of the following form (orthogonal to the kernel):

$$[[\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}]_0 = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\sigma} c^2 \\ \bar{\sigma} s^2 \\ \bar{\tau} \sqrt{2} sc \end{bmatrix}$$

in which $\bar{\sigma}$ and $\bar{\tau}$ are two arbitrary parameters. Obviously, this does not define the most general loading: a completely arbitrary state of stress $(\bar{\sigma}_{11}, \bar{\sigma}_{22}, \bar{\sigma}_{12})$ generally includes a part proportional to the kernel, and so cannot be supported by the structure

Limiting to the type of loads bearable by the structure, the longitudinal stresses in the plies, according to the general formula, are:

$$\sigma_{\varphi\varphi}^0 = \bar{\sigma} + \bar{\tau} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_{-\varphi-\varphi}^0 = \bar{\sigma} - \bar{\tau}$$

4.3 Three-ply reinforcement

Any stacking sequence with 3 distinct directions of reinforcement has a regular stiffness matrix. So a three-ply reinforced structure can support any load, the plies being loaded in the direction of their fibers, at possibly different levels.

A particular case is considered here, with 3 plies at 45 degrees, or stacking sequence $[0/\pm 45]$. The mean stiffness, obtained from the CLPT, is in the overall axes:

$$[\bar{\mathbf{Q}}]_0 = \frac{E}{6} \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix}$$

from which the compliance matrix in the same axes is easily computed as the (usual) inverse:

$$[\bar{\mathbf{S}}]_0 = \frac{3}{E} \begin{bmatrix} +1 & -1 & 0 \\ -1 & +3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & +1 \end{bmatrix}$$

With the general formula, one gets the unidirectional stress in each ply:

- for the 0° ply, $\sigma_{00}^0 = 3(\bar{\sigma}_{11} - \bar{\sigma}_{22})$,
- for the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies, $\sigma_{\pm\pm}^\pm = 3(\bar{\sigma}_{22} \pm \bar{\sigma}_{12})$.

5 An example : the cylindrical pressure vessel

A classical application of the netting theory is the sizing of closed cylindrical pressure vessels.

When the thickness e of the vessel is small compared to the radius R , it is well known from elementary equilibrium equations that, in such vessels with internal pressure P , the mean hoop stress equals two times the mean longitudinal stress :

$$\bar{\sigma}_{11} = 2\bar{\sigma}_{22} = 2\Sigma$$

with axis 1 along the hoop direction, axis 2 along the axial direction, and $2\Sigma = PR/e$.

Then the netting theory rules that fibers must be wound at some opposite angles $\pm\theta_M$ from the axial direction. This mysterious angle θ_M , which value is given with the surprising precision of $54,74^\circ$, is in fact identical to the "magic angle" encountered in several questions of theoretical physics and mathematics and defined from the equation $\cos^2\theta_M = 1/3$.

Applying the results developed above in this paper, we will show that this design is in some sense optimal, but not robust, and that other optimal designs can be obtained. Three designs (cross-ply, angle-ply and angle-ply with extra hoop ply) are considered and compared for the above loading, which writes :

$$[\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}]_0 = \Sigma \begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

In the following, we use the quite natural optimality criterion which requires *all the plies to be loaded at the same level*, each in its local axes.

5.1 Cross-ply design

The loading has the form required to be supported by the structure. The optimal design is obtained by selecting the proportion p in order to satisfy the optimality criterion:

$$\sigma_{00}^0 = \sigma_{9090}^0$$

that is:

$$\frac{2\Sigma}{p} = \frac{2\Sigma}{1-p} \quad \text{or} \quad p = \frac{2}{3}$$

The optimal cross-ply solution has two fibers in the hoop direction for one in the axial direction, with the stacking sequence $[0_{2n}/90_n]$.

As expected, all the plies have the same unidirectional stress:

$$\sigma_{00}^0 = \sigma_{9090}^0 = 3\Sigma$$

The mean stiffness is:

$$[\bar{\mathbf{Q}}]_0 = \frac{E}{3} \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

5.2 Angle-ply design

In the optimal angle-ply configuration $[\pm\varphi_M]$, the parameters are defined by the equation:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \bar{\sigma} c^2 \\ \bar{\sigma} s^2 \\ \bar{\tau}\sqrt{2}sc \end{bmatrix} = \Sigma \begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

which gives $\bar{\sigma} = 3\Sigma$, $\bar{\tau} = 0$, and $\cos^2\varphi = 2/3$.

So the optimal angle of the fibers with the hoop direction is the complementary angle of the "magic angle":

$$\varphi_M = 90^\circ - \theta_M$$

which is exactly the classical solution of the netting analysis, as presented above. The netting analysis is in fact an optimal design analysis.

Coming now to the common value of the longitudinal stress in the plies, one finds:

$$\sigma_{++}^+ = \sigma_{--}^- = 3\Sigma$$

which is exactly the same value as in the optimal cross-ply case, while the mean stiffness is:

$$[\bar{\mathbf{Q}}]_0 = \frac{E}{9} \begin{bmatrix} 4 & 2 & 0 \\ 2 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 4 \end{bmatrix}$$

5.3 Three-direction design

Limiting to the simple sequence $[0/\pm 45]$ studied above, it is found that it satisfies exactly the optimality criterion, as the three plies have the same longitudinal stress under the pressure loading:

$$\sigma_{00}^0 = \sigma_{\pm\pm}^\pm = 3\Sigma$$

which is again the same as in the two previous optimal designs. The mean stiffness equals :

$$[\bar{\mathbf{Q}}]_0 = \frac{E}{6} \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix}$$

More generally, tridirectional reinforcements depend on five design parameters (3 angles and 3 proportions totaling 100%) and can be adjusted to the optimality criterion. Specially convenient is the family combining cross-ply plus hoop ply, with sequences $[0_{1-2p}/\pm\omega_p]$, which has two independent parameters, p and ω , and so can satisfy the equal stress criterion plus an extra condition.

5.4 Comparison of the three optimal designs

The optimal designs derived above for these three configurations are equivalent in efficiency: the same total thickness is required to support the same pressure.

However, a general question arising in optimization is the stability of solutions and their sensitivity to perturbations. With respect to this issue, the three designs are far from equivalent. The fact that these optimal configurations have different stiffness matrices shows that they generally

behave differently although they behave the same for the special design loading defined by Σ .

Having singular stiffness matrices, the two-direction structures behave optimally as predicted only for perfect conditions: perfect alignment and proportion of fibers, perfect direction of loading. It can be shown that even perfect structures cannot accommodate arbitrary load fluctuations. Conversely, arbitrary fluctuations in the stacking can induce instability even for perfectly aligned loading.

On contrary, three-direction structures are not so sensitive to load variations and also their mechanical properties are not so sensitive to stacking fluctuations.

6 Comments

The present work shows that the netting theory is reproduced when applying the laminated structure theory in the limit case of a very simplified stress-strain relationship. More, while the implementation of the netting analysis is cumbersome for more than two directions, the limit case of CLPT provides a systematic method in any case.

Conversely, what could be the contribution of netting theory (or limit case of CLPT) to composite structures? Due to its simplification, the limit case of CLPT allows the derivation of close-form solutions (as above for the optimisation of pressure vessel). They are exact only under the assumptions of the netting theory, however they certainly can be approximations of the real situation for composites and can give trends for ply stress evaluation and for optimisation of design. Specially, the singular total stiffnesses which result in some cases might be very significant: laminates with only two-direction reinforcement could be very sensitive to some combinations of loads and these critical states can be found, or at least estimated, using the limit case.

In conclusion, the netting theory and the laminated structure theory should not be opposed, as they may offer mutual contributions.

References

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APPENDIX

Appendix A-1: Notations

All physical quantities have a tensorial character, however for convenience reasons, their components are generally stored in matrix forms, according to conventional rules. The matrix forms presently used are detailed hereafter.

Further, for laminated structures, it is well known that several systems of axes are used: typically the axes of the laminate (overall axes in which the external loads and boundary conditions are applied), and the local axes of each ply (in which local stresses and failure criteria are easily computed). It is necessary to refer clearly to these systems of axes as well as the ply which is concerned.

Referring to axes: In the present work, a *subscript* is used to refer to the axes in which the components are expressed. Subscript $_0$ refers to the overall axes.

A *superscript* is used to refer to the ply.

For instance, $[[\boldsymbol{\sigma}]]_0^\varphi$ is the stress matrix in the laminate axes of a ply oriented in direction φ , while $[[\boldsymbol{\sigma}]]_\varphi^\varphi$ is the stress matrix of the same ply in its local axes. Similarly, $[[\mathbf{Q}]]_0^\varphi$ is the stiffness matrix in the laminate axes of this ply of direction φ , while $[[\mathbf{Q}]]_\varphi^\varphi$ is the stiffness matrix of the same ply in its local axes.

For rotation matrices, two subscripts are used to refer to the old and new systems of axes. An ar-

row between the two subscripts makes clear their meanings, old or new.

Matrix notations: The classical Voigt notations differ from strains and compliances on one side, and stresses and stiffnesses on the other side. Here we use a variant, in which the tensorial components of strains and stresses, as well as the components of compliances and stiffnesses are treated similarly, as illustrated hereafter. Double brackets are used for present notations to distinguish from Voigt notations.

Voigt notations:

$$\{\boldsymbol{\sigma}\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} \\ \varepsilon_{22} \\ 2\varepsilon_{12} \end{Bmatrix}$$

$$\{\mathbf{Q}\} = \begin{Bmatrix} Q_{1111} & Q_{1122} & Q_{1112} \\ Q_{1122} & Q_{2222} & Q_{1222} \\ Q_{1112} & Q_{1222} & Q_{1212} \end{Bmatrix}$$

$$\{\mathbf{S}\} = \begin{Bmatrix} S_{1111} & S_{1122} & 2S_{1112} \\ S_{1122} & S_{2222} & 2S_{1222} \\ 2S_{1112} & 2S_{1222} & 4S_{1212} \end{Bmatrix}$$

Present notations:

$$[[\boldsymbol{\sigma}]] = \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sqrt{2}\sigma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad [[\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}]] = \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} \\ \varepsilon_{22} \\ \sqrt{2}\varepsilon_{12} \end{Bmatrix}$$

$$[[\mathbf{Q}]] = \begin{Bmatrix} Q_{1111} & Q_{1122} & \sqrt{2}Q_{1112} \\ Q_{1122} & Q_{2222} & \sqrt{2}Q_{1222} \\ \sqrt{2}Q_{1112} & \sqrt{2}Q_{1222} & 2Q_{1212} \end{Bmatrix}$$

$$[[\mathbf{S}]] = \begin{bmatrix} S_{1111} & S_{1122} & \sqrt{2} S_{1112} \\ S_{1122} & S_{2222} & \sqrt{2} S_{1222} \\ \sqrt{2} S_{1112} & \sqrt{2} S_{1222} & 2 S_{1212} \end{bmatrix}$$

Both notations are consistent with the classical form for stress-strain relationships:

$$\{\boldsymbol{\sigma}\} = \{\mathbf{Q}\} \{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}\} \quad \text{and} \quad \{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}\} = \{\mathbf{S}\} \{\boldsymbol{\sigma}\}$$

$$[[\boldsymbol{\sigma}]] = [[\mathbf{Q}]] [[\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}]] \quad \text{and} \quad [[\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}]] = [[\mathbf{S}]] [[\boldsymbol{\sigma}]]$$

Change of axes: Differences between Voigt and present notations appear when rotations are applied for changing axes. We specially consider here a rotation by an angle φ from overall axes (with subscript $_0$) to local axes (with subscript $_\varphi$). Let us have $c = \cos \varphi$, $S = \sin \varphi$, $C = \cos 2\varphi$ and $S = \sin 2\varphi$.

With the present notation, the rotation matrices are orthogonal matrices, the same for all the quantities:

$$[[\mathbf{R}]]_{\varphi \leftarrow 0} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1+C}{2} & \frac{1-C}{2} & +\frac{S}{\sqrt{2}} \\ \frac{1-C}{2} & \frac{1+C}{2} & -\frac{S}{\sqrt{2}} \\ -\frac{S}{\sqrt{2}} & +\frac{S}{\sqrt{2}} & C \end{bmatrix}$$

or also:

$$[[\mathbf{R}]]_{\varphi \leftarrow 0} = \begin{bmatrix} c^2 & s^2 & +\sqrt{2} sc \\ s^2 & c^2 & -\sqrt{2} sc \\ -\sqrt{2} sc & +\sqrt{2} sc & c^2 - s^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

As orthogonal matrices, they satisfy

$$[[\mathbf{R}]]_{\varphi \leftarrow 0}^{-1} = [[\mathbf{R}]]_{\varphi \leftarrow 0}^T$$

and they act as:

$$[[\boldsymbol{\sigma}]]_{\varphi} = [[\mathbf{R}]]_{\varphi \leftarrow 0} [[\boldsymbol{\sigma}]]_0 \quad [[\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}]]_{\varphi} = [[\mathbf{R}]]_{\varphi \leftarrow 0} [[\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}]]_0$$

$$[[\mathbf{Q}]]_{\varphi} = [[\mathbf{R}]]_{\varphi \leftarrow 0} [[\mathbf{Q}]]_0 [[\mathbf{R}]]_{0 \leftarrow \varphi}$$

$$[[\mathbf{S}]]_{\varphi} = [[\mathbf{R}]]_{\varphi \leftarrow 0} [[\mathbf{S}]]_0 [[\mathbf{R}]]_{0 \leftarrow \varphi}$$

With Voigt notations, the rotation matrices are different for stress vectors and strain vectors. Their values are presented in every textbook on composite materials ([1], [2]).

For stress:

$$\{\mathbf{R}\}_{\varphi \leftarrow 0}^{\sigma} = \begin{bmatrix} c^2 & s^2 & +2sc \\ s^2 & c^2 & -2sc \\ -sc & +sc & c^2 - s^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

and for strain:

$$\{\mathbf{R}\}_{\varphi \leftarrow 0}^{\varepsilon} = \begin{bmatrix} c^2 & s^2 & +sc \\ s^2 & c^2 & -sc \\ -2sc & +2sc & c^2 - s^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

These matrices are unimodular but not orthogonal. They act as follows:

$$\{\boldsymbol{\sigma}\}_{\varphi} = \{\mathbf{R}\}_{\varphi \leftarrow 0}^{\sigma} \{\boldsymbol{\sigma}\}_0 \quad \{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}\}_{\varphi} = \{\mathbf{R}\}_{\varphi \leftarrow 0}^{\varepsilon} \{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}\}_0$$

$$\{\mathbf{Q}\}_{\varphi} = \{\mathbf{R}\}_{\varphi \leftarrow 0}^{\sigma} \{\mathbf{Q}\}_0 \{\mathbf{R}\}_{0 \leftarrow \varphi}^{\varepsilon}$$

$$\{\mathbf{S}\}_{\varphi} = \{\mathbf{R}\}_{\varphi \leftarrow 0}^{\varepsilon} \{\mathbf{S}\}_0 \{\mathbf{R}\}_{0 \leftarrow \varphi}^{\sigma}$$

Appendix A-2: Singular stiffness and compliance matrices

When the stiffness matrix is singular, as it is always the case with two-direction reinforcement in the netting theory, it is still possible to define a compliance matrix using the mathematical concepts of generalized inverses.

Several generalizations of the inversion for singular matrices have been introduced by mathematicians, under the names of generalized inverse or pseudoinverse. They are now commonly presented in textbooks [6]. The Moore-Penrose pseudoinverse could be specially useful in structural mechanics. Presentation is here limited to a square symmetric singular matrix \mathbf{Q} with normalized kernel (or null space vectors) \mathbf{K}_n (so $\mathbf{K}_n^T \mathbf{K}_n = \mathbf{I}$). Then the Moore-Penrose pseudoinverse of \mathbf{Q} is a square symmetric singular matrix \mathbf{S} with same kernel, which satisfies the following equations:

$$\mathbf{Q} \mathbf{S} \mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{Q}$$

$$\mathbf{S} \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{S} = \mathbf{S}$$

$$\mathbf{Q} \mathbf{S} = \mathbf{S} \mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_n \mathbf{K}_n^T$$

While the concept of generalized inverse is well established, its actual construction is generally not easy and refers to sophisticated mathematical methods like the singular value decomposition, which limits the practical applications.

However, for mechanical applications, the author has developed [7] a three-step method to compute the pseudoinverse of a singular symmetric matrix \mathbf{Q} in the case its kernel \mathbf{K}_n is known.

The first step introduces a regularization of the singular matrix \mathbf{Q} :

$$\mathbf{Q}^* = \mathbf{Q} + \alpha \mathbf{K}_n \mathbf{K}_n^T$$

in which α is a non-zero, otherwise arbitrary parameter.

In the second step, as this matrix \mathbf{Q}^* is regular, it can be inverted (in the classical sense), which gives:

$$\mathbf{S}^* = (\mathbf{Q}^*)^{-1}$$

In the third step, it occurs that this regular matrix \mathbf{S}^* is the regularization with parameter α^{-1} of the pseudo inverse \mathbf{S} of the initial singular matrix \mathbf{S} :

$$\mathbf{S}^* = \mathbf{S} + \alpha^{-1} \mathbf{K}_n \mathbf{K}_n^T$$

from which the pseudoinverse \mathbf{S} is obtained.

These three steps can be condensed in a unique formula :

$$\mathbf{S} = (\mathbf{Q} + \alpha \mathbf{K}_n \mathbf{K}_n^T)^{-1} - \alpha^{-1} \mathbf{R}_0 \mathbf{R}_0^T$$

however the three-step process is easier to use for practical purpose.

Now, if we have some linear relationship between two sets of variables $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{Q} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$$

it results from the properties of the pseudoinverse that we have also the inverse relationship:

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \mathbf{S} \boldsymbol{\sigma}$$

it for any set of variables $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ orthogonal to the kernel. No meaning can be obtained for other variables $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$.

This reveals the meaning of the pseudoinverse, which appears to be the *singular compliance matrix* associated to the *singular stiffness matrix* and restricted to variables compatible with the structural behaviour.

An example of computation of the generalized compliance: For the $[\pm\varphi]$ stacking sequence, the mean stiffness is:

$$\bar{\mathbf{Q}} = E \begin{bmatrix} c^4 & s^2 c^2 & 0 \\ s^2 c^2 & s^4 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2s^2 c^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

in which $c = \cos \varphi$ and $s = \sin \varphi$.

For $0 < \varphi < \pi/4$, its rank equals 2 and its normalized kernel is:

$$\mathbf{K}_n = \frac{1}{\sqrt{c^4 + s^4}} \begin{bmatrix} +s^2 \\ -c^2 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

from which:

$$\mathbf{K}_n \mathbf{K}_n^T = \frac{1}{c^4 + s^4} \begin{bmatrix} s^4 & -s^2 c^2 & 0 \\ -s^2 c^2 & c^4 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

It is very convenient to select α as follows:

$$\alpha = E(c^4 + s^4)$$

for it makes diagonal the regularized stiffness $\bar{\mathbf{Q}}^* = \bar{\mathbf{Q}} + \alpha \mathbf{K}_n \mathbf{K}_n^T$:

$$\bar{\mathbf{Q}}^* = E \begin{bmatrix} c^4 + s^4 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & c^4 + s^4 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2s^2 c^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

easily inverted into the regularized compliance:

$$\bar{\mathbf{S}}^* = \frac{1}{E} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{c^4 + s^4} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{c^4 + s^4} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2s^2 c^2} \end{bmatrix}$$

As the compliance is $\bar{\mathbf{S}} = \bar{\mathbf{S}}^* - \alpha^{-1} \mathbf{K}_n \mathbf{K}_n^T$, it follows :

$$\bar{\mathbf{S}} = \frac{1}{E} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{c^4}{(c^4 + s^4)^2} & \frac{s^2 c^2}{(c^4 + s^4)^2} & 0 \\ \frac{s^2 c^2}{(c^4 + s^4)^2} & \frac{s^4}{(c^4 + s^4)^2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2s^2 c^2} \end{bmatrix}$$

Like the mean stiffness, this mean compliance is singular, with rank 2 and normalized kernel \mathbf{K}_n .